

MEASURES TO PREVENT AND TREAT LYMPHADENITIS DISEASE.

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Abstract: Lymphadenitis is an inflammation of the lymph nodes that occurs as a result of a reaction to a chronic or aggravated serious disease in the body. A lymph node is a collection of lymph vessels that produce specialized cells to fight infection, organ or tissue disease. In this article, we will inform people about lymphadenitis, that is, the disease, its types, causes, treatment, etc.

Key words: Lymphadenitis, causes of lymphadenitis, types, symptoms, diagnosis, treatment.

Main part: Lymphadenitis (lymph and wool. aden — gland) — inflammation of lymph nodes. When lymph nodes are infected with inflammatory microbes and their toxins, they become a complication, that is, as a secondary disease.

Types and stages of lymphadenitis

Classification of lymphadenitis includes distinguishing such types of this disease: acute lymphadenitis, which occurs with rapid infections (for example, with tonsillitis); chronic lymphadenitis with chronic infections (tuberculosis, HIV infection), oncological diseases. Acute or reactive lymphadenitis goes through several stages: catarrhal (increased blood circulation, infiltration of the lymph node with immune cells);

hyperplastic (increased lymphoid tissue); purulent (necrosis of nodal tissue with ongoing severe inflammation).

Purulent lymphadenitis can be accompanied by an abscess of the node and penetration of pus into the surrounding tissues. More severe forms of the

disease are fibrinosis (with impregnation of the organ with fibrin), icherosis (rotten decay), hemorrhagic (absorption of blood), necrotic (rapid necrosis of lymph node tissue).

Nonspecific process is caused by staphylococci, streptococci and other common microorganisms. Special lymphadenitis is usually called tuberculous lesions of the lymph node. Treatment of lymphadenitis should begin immediately when its first symptoms appear. Specialists of the chain of Mama Papa Ya family polyclinics help the patient. Doctors not only diagnose and choose treatment, but also determine the cause of the disease.

Cause of lymphadenitis

Swollen and enlarged lymph nodes can be caused by a serious disease that affects the lymphatic system or organs near the inflamed lymph nodes. In the first case, the infection enters the lymph node, and in the second case, the lymph node actively starts producing lymphocytes to fight against the strong threat.

Acute respiratory viral infections, infectious, bacterial and fungal diseases of any organs, HIV, presence of parasites in the body, cholera, anthrax, autoimmune diseases, immune disorders, any acute inflammation, lymphoma and any oncological metastases in the organ can cause lymphadenitis.

A pathogen can enter any organ in the body through the lymphatic system. Therefore, lymphadenitis is dangerous. In addition, if you do not pay attention to the inflamed node, it will soon start the inflammatory process in other tissues - and then it will be much more difficult to find the starting point of the disease.

People with weak immunity, people with allergies, people suffering from chronic alcoholism, people with thyroid disease and hormonal diseases are at risk of developing lymphadenitis.

Symptoms

Normally, lymph nodes are not felt or are felt only as elastic balls under the skin. Depending on the cause of lymphadenitis, various symptoms may appear:

- enlarged lymph nodes;
- redness of the skin in the area of damage to the lymph nodes;
- pain when touching the lymph node;
- joining of nodes with each other;
- high temperature;
- fusion and expansion of lymph nodes with adjacent tissue;

The disease can cause fever, weakness and poisoning.

If lymphadenitis is caused by some disease, then the first symptoms shown during acute lymphadenitis appear, and in chronic lymphadenitis - all symptoms

from this list appear. Therefore, if both diseases are missed at the initial level, it will be more difficult to treat chronic lymphadenitis.

Tuberculosis and syphilis usually cause chronic lymphadenitis. Bacteria and fungi cause acute lymphadenitis, which later causes thrombophlebitis.

However, swollen lymph nodes can also be caused by a weakened immune system. In this case, there are no serious diseases in the body. Such a combination can cause an autoimmune disease, so this condition is also serious and dangerous.

Diagnosis

Often, the doctor determines lymphadenitis after examination, anamnesis and palpation of the lymph nodes, but biochemical and general blood analysis and ultrasound examination are often prescribed. A complete examination of the nose and throat is carried out to identify possible diseases in this area. A biopsy or additional body fluid tests may also be ordered. Analysis of lymph node material allows to exclude not only diseases, but also cancer and other serious infectious diseases.

Treatment

Usually, treatment is carried out conservatively with drugs. However, in cases of severe disease, surgical intervention is possible.

After the diagnosis, the doctor prescribes antibiotic drugs for bacteria, and for infectious cases, the treatment of the main infection (prescribing antibiotics, sedatives, pain relievers, anti-inflammatory drugs, etc.) and the pain of the affected lymph node. He prescribes drugs to relieve his pain. In outpatient treatment at home, ointments that affect the skin and subcutaneous tissue are often used to speed up treatment. In addition, in most cases, it is mandatory to increase the water regime, if there is physical activity, it is prescribed to reduce it and special diets.

If the cause of the disease is a severe infection and the lymph nodes cannot be treated by conservative methods, they should be removed. Sometimes for treatment, lymph nodes are opened, drained and cleaned. If there are benign tumors, it will be removed or monitored. If cancer is the cause of lymphadenitis, doctors focus on treating the cancer.

After surgery, the doctor also prescribes additional treatment therapy, which includes broad-spectrum antibiotics (for example, macrolides), antihistamines, anti-inflammatory and pain relievers.

Summary: Lymphadenitis appears as a reaction to a missed or chronic disease. Therefore, timely and complete treatment of diseases is necessary to prevent the

disease. It is not necessary to arbitrarily treat purulent wounds, infectious and bacteriological diseases. Protect yourself from injuries. People at risk of disease: people with immunodeficiency, chronic diseases, always suffering from ARVI.

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